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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study				The molecular mechanism of on-demand sterol biosynthesis at organelle contact sites-1			
Document creation date		10/20/2025		Principal investigator		Britta Brügger / Heidelberg Lipidomics	
Institution		Heidelberg University Biochemistry Center (BZH)		Corresponding Email		britta.bruegger@bzh.uni-heidelberg.de	
Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?		Targeted		Clinical		No	

Lipid extraction

Extraction method		2-phase system		pH adjustment		Hydrochloric acid	
2-phase system		Bligh&Dyer		Special conditions		Neutral Bligh&Dyer for the analysis of ergosteryl esters	
Derivatization		Acetylation of free ergosterol, no derivatization of ergosteryl esters		Were internal standards added prior extraction?		Yes	

Analytical platform

Ionization additives		Ammonium acetate		Detector		Mass spectrometer	
MS type		QTrap		MS vendor		SCIEX	
Direct type		Chip		MS Level		MS ²	
Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)		1		Mass resolution for detected ion at MS ²		Low resolution	
Resolution at MS ²		Unit		Recording mode of raw data at MS ²		Profile mode	
Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used		No					

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Solvent blank, Internal standard blank
Quality control	Yes	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Lipid recovery	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	No	Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	No
Precision	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Guidelines followed	None		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Are metadata available?	Available on request
Raw data upload	Available on request	Additional comments	Raw data will be uploaded to MetaboLights

Sample Descriptions

Control/OE Yet3 / Fungi / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze, Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles
Temperature handling original sample	4-8 °C	Instant sample preparation	No
Time to freeze	between 5 and 40 min	Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes
Storage temperature	-80 °C	Storage time (month)	0
Freeze-thaw cycles	1	Additives	None
Were samples stored under inert gas?	No	Additional preservation methods	No
Biobank samples	No		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) ST[M]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ST	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ² adduct	[M] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name			
-FA 2:0(+HO)-Ergosterol(35)			
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	Lipidview 1.3
Data manipulation	Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No

Nomenclature for fragment ions	Yes	Further identification remarks	Derivatization of sterols with acetyl chloride to sterol acetate.
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1) ST[M]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
d5-ST29:2;O	-FA 2:0(+HO)-d5-Stigmasterol(35)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	One factor for all species
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView 1.3 and homemade
Batch correction	No		

2) SE[M]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SE	MS Level for identification	MS ²
Identification level	Molecular species level	MS ² adduct	[M] ⁺
Fragments for identification			
Fragment name	-FAx:y(+HO)-Ergosterol(35)		
Isotope correction at MS ²	Type 2	MS ² verified by standard	Yes
Background check at MS ²	Yes	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
Limit of detection	No	Lipid Identification Software	LipidView 1.3
Data manipulation	Background subtraction	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A		

2) SE[M]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	MS Level for quantification	MS ²
Internal lipid standard(s) MS ²			
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
SE 28:3;O/19:0	-FA19:0(+HO)-Ergosterol(35)		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Response correction	One factor for all species
Type I isotope correction	Yes	Limit of quantification	No
Normalization to reference	No	Lipid Quantification Software	LipidView 1.3
Batch correction	No		